

The Impact Of Teachers' Perceptions On Organizational Dna To Organizational Commitment

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 03, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 05, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Organizational DNA, Organizational Commitment, Organizational Behaviour</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5550655</p>	<p><i>Organizational DNA is defined as the vision, values, and sense of orientation that enables employees to understand and embrace the purpose and strength of the organization and hold the organization together. The main purpose of this research is to reveal the relationship between public employees' perceptions of organizational DNA and their organizational commitment. In line with the sub-objectives determined in accordance with the main purpose, the research was designed using the correlational survey model, one of the quantitative research methods. The universe of the research consists of staff working in public institutions and organizations located in Mersin province and Tarsus district. The data were collected by the convenience sampling method. It has been concluded that the perception of organizational DNA differs according to gender, seniority, age and education. On the other hand, the level of organizational commitment of public employees has also been relatively high, which differs according to the seniority and age variables. Finally, the results showed that there is a significant relationship between perception of organizational DNA and organizational commitment.</i></p>

Introduction

The word "organization" is derived from English and has the meaning of organizing. An organization can be defined as a group of people or institutions organized and united for a purpose. Organizations are structures that have characteristics within themselves and, thanks to these characteristics, try to bring their members together around them. One of the first things that comes to mind for the basic characteristics that distinguish organizations from other phenomena is that they are created as an open system whose input and output are simultaneously human.

Although the concept of system has a very broad meaning, it can be explained as continuous relationships between multiple entities (Akkuş & İzci, 2018). Open systems export these outputs to their environment. Open systems are not stationary, but are organized to survive continuously, open to change, development and growth (Yalçınkaya, 2002). In this sense, institutions process the inputs they obtain from their environment and the society they are in and transform them into outputs.

First of all, it is envisaged that organizations will transform the individuals who make up them into systems that meet their purpose and, moreover, bring these systems together in harmony with one another in order to become a holistic organization. This whole process is undoubtedly accompanied by a number of elements, so the organization is actually the final picture that occurs as a result of the interaction of multiple elements and systems (Çetin, 2014). In this sense, the existence of an organization in the educational process, in which both its input and output are human, that is, a continuously variable entity, plays a leading role, is based on the human element. Since the human is the leading factor in the organization, many concepts related to people have been adapted to the organization and eventually the organization has emerged as a living entity. Each organization has a predetermined service concept, philosophy, business style, in short, a cultural infrastructure (Çetin & Döş, 2014).

The fact that organizations are composed of people has enabled the transfer of human characteristics to the organization and the acceptance of organizations as living organisms. Such developments enable organizations to analyze and understand their operational processes more clearly.

One of the main pillars of the approach to treating organizations as living organisms is the effort to explain organizational life through metaphors. Metaphor is used in colloquial language in the form of metaphor and simulation. Nevertheless, it is basically used to build a transformation between concepts in the form of using a more popular or leaner concept to explain a little-known or complex concept. When using metaphors, people can also express phenomena that have a metaphorical meaning, reflect reality, or have a completely different meaning. An analogy can mean the same thing for everyone, but it can also have different meanings (Namlı et al., 2017). Therefore, it is possible to explain the structure and functioning of the organization with metaphors.

Literature review and development of conceptual framework

Organizational DNA

Various applications and methods have been developed to identify the structures of organizations and determine their characteristics. One of the tools used to identify organizations is organizational DNA (Çetin, 2014). Accordingly, the concept of DNA, which refers to the code system of cells, which is the basic building block of living things, is used as a metaphor by adapting it to organizations in a real or lateral sense. From a biological point of view, human DNA is a database that shows characteristics that distinguish it from others, and also transmits genetic information from generation to generation. From this point of view, organizational DNA refers to a structure that resembles human DNA, distinguishes organizations from others, determines how they work, and considers them as the same organism in terms of their ability to survive. Shortly, when it is called organizational DNA, it can be stated that the DNA and its components that distinguish people from each other are valid within organizations, and each organization has its own unique structure.

Like the DNA of living organisms, organizational DNA consists of four building blocks, which combine and recombine to express different identities and personalities. These organizational building blocks – structure, decision rights, motivators, and information – largely determine how a firm looks and behaves, internally and externally (Neilson et al., 2004):

- **Structure:** *What is the hierarchical structure of the organization? How many layers does the organization consist of interconnected or independent?*
- **Decision rights:** *Who decides what, and how? How does anyone participate in the decision-making process? What are the limits of a person's decision-making power?*
- **Motivators:** *What are the goals of the members, and their career plans? How are members motivated financially and spiritually?*
- **Information:** *What criteria are used to determine performance? How activities are organized? How is the flow of information provided?*

Since organizations also have building blocks, it can be argued that the building blocks mentioned in the organization's DNA have a function such as the four nucleic acids in human DNA. When these four basic building blocks are examined in the context of the organizational DNA, it can be mentioned that there are understandings that are not very different from each other, but consider organizations with various nuances (Çetin & Döş, 2014). According to Çandır (2005), one of the most important features of DNA is that it transfers the characteristics of the organization to future generations. The human body stores the information it needs to perform all activities from the fetal state to death in DNA and transmits it to future generations. According to these characteristics, organizations can have different profiles. A study called "organizational DNA profiles", developed by researchers at the BoozAllen company in 2013, revealed seven different organizational DNA profiles, four of which were unhealthy and three of which were healthy, based on the responses of participants. The seven types of organizational DNA identified by Neilson, Pasternack, & Mendes (2003) are as follows: (1) the resilient organization, (2) the just-in-time organization, (3) the military organization, (4) the passive-aggressive organization, (5) the fits-and-starts organization, (6) the outgrown organization and (7) the overmanaged organization.

Unhealthy organization DNA profiles

Four out of a total of seven organizational DNA profiles are described as unhealthy: (1) passive-aggressive organizations, (2) fits-and-starts organizations, (3) outgrown organizations and (4) overmanaged organizations.

The passive-aggressive organization: At first glance, everything seems routine and ordinary in this type of organization. One of the prominent points in these organizations is that there is a harmonious and conflict-free climate among employees, but the decision-making mechanism on critical issues does not work well and ideas for change cannot be implemented (Kahraman, 2019). In other words, in this type of organization, "everyone agrees, but nothing changes." In such organizations, behind the quiet, calm and harmonious workforce, which attracts attention at first glance, lies inadequate decision-making and change crises. Therefore, there is usually a situation in which decision makers do not comply with decisions and therefore change due to lack of information and distrust for the organization (Çetin, 2014).

The fits-and-starts organization: It can be stated that in such organizations, as the name suggests, they lack the ability to make sound decisions and transform the decisions taken into long-term strategies. These organizations provide an environment for entrepreneurs and intelligent people to come up with an idea and implement it without restrictions. However, in a place where there is no strong direction from the top and no common values, it is observed that these ideas conflict with each other and disappear or gradually disappear. As a result, an organization that has spread excessively and is about to get out of control (Kahraman, 2019). Therefore, there is

a particular problem of stability in this type of organization, and employees have various concerns about what exactly is going on in the decision making process.

The outgrown organization: This type of organization, as its name suggests, refers to a work environment that has grown hierarchically overgrown, divided into numerous levels, and can no longer be effectively managed. In other words, the organization spreads too much and goes beyond the boundaries of decision-making and implementation, and therefore becomes increasingly difficult to control. An outgrown organization has been made too large and complex to be managed by a core team, and therefore it is almost impossible to democratize its management (Çandır, 2005). Especially due to the scattered organizational structure, the overgrowth of organizations trying to centralize their decision-making powers, on the other hand, causes the organization to miss opportunities and the intermediary managers to be unable to take initiative (Neilson et al., 2004).

The overmanaged organization: It is a practice that makes its existence feel excessive, rather than an effective management mechanism, the basic assumption in the type of overmanaged organization. The presence of excessive layers of management in such organizations leads to the damage of managerial moves to the holistic structure of the organization and makes the already heavily functioning decision-making mechanism even more chaotic (Çetin, 2014). On the other hand, these types of organizations, which often have a bureaucratic and political nature, tend to block energetic and result-oriented people and disappoint them (Kahraman, 2019). It can be stated that in overmanaged organizations, there is a situation of conflict between managers and employees, but these conflicts are caused by task titles rather than people. In other words, even if the person serving as a manager in any position changes, the new manager who will replace him/her is likely to be a party to similar conflicts due to the power brought by the position title, regardless of personality traits. In such organizations, there is a lot of waste of labor and information in idle state, but the degree of influence of the manager is due to his/her title and position and there is no cooperation between units (Bancar, 2016).

Healthy organization DNA profiles

In total, three of the seven organizational DNA profiles are described as healthy: (1) just-in-time organizations, (2) military organizations and (3) resilient organizations.

The just in time organization: These organizations are not proactive in adapting to changes, but can make sudden maneuvers without losing sight of the big picture. While these organizations manage to retain people and perform well financially, they cannot leap from good to great (Kahraman, 2019). Just-in-time organizations have a distinctive culture that adds a competitive spirit to it, so they motivate people who work within it with their shared vision by integrating them into that culture (BoozAllen, 2013). In other words, although things do not work perfectly in this type of organization, there are no large-scale failures and a neglected victim of leadership.

The military organization: It is a type of organization that is managed by a small group of top managers and works just like a machine. In these organizations, which have a highly hierarchical structure, everyone knows the job they will do very well and performs it with great care (Kahraman, 2019). The structure of this type of organization has a horizontal and vertical hierarchy, but this hierarchy does not create tension between the management layers (Bostancı & Tosun, 2019). In other words, the division of labor is carried out within the organization and the job descriptions of the employees are made. Everyone knows their role well and performs their part properly (Çetin & Döş, 2014), so that there is no chaos in the organization.

The resilient organization: These organizations are not stuck in a strict vision and mission. It is the type of organization that adapts best to environmental changes. In other words, this type of organization is flexible enough to adapt quickly to external market shifts, yet it remains steadfastly focused on and aligned with a coherent business strategy (Kahraman, 2019). Thus, social changes or market fluctuations are not the main threats to these organizations; on the contrary, they keep the organization alive by closely following the transformation experienced by society with the understanding of turning a crisis into an opportunity. On the other hand, this type of organization, which can easily adapt to environmental changes, can create innovations by solving problems thanks to its flexible structures and constantly renew itself in the future (Bostancı & Tosun, 2019). In this way, innovations that are the cause or the result of each change become actually desirable situations for such organizations.

Organizational commitment

Organic members of an organization have some responsibilities for the sustainability of the organization's existence. In this sense, the existence of social open systems basically depends on their continuous development and the sense of sustainable trust and need in the society. Therefore, it is possible for employees to allocate this

trust and meet the needs by establishing the organization-member interaction in a healthy way. One of the highlights in this fiction is organizational commitment. It is possible to define organizational commitment as employees' desire to stay in the organization, identification with all the effectiveness, interest and success of the organization, employees' commitment to the organization, attitudes and interests towards the organization they work for to be successful (Bayram, 2005). Organizational commitment has become an important issue for institutions for many reasons: (1) absenteeism, abandonment of work, withdrawal behavior with job search activities; (2) clinging to work, job satisfaction, emotional and mental structures and (3) the characteristics of the employee's work, such as participation, responsibility, and the fourth is the benefits of knowing the elements of organizational commitment that the employee adopts with their personal factors to the organization (Balay, 2017; Kahveci et al., 2019).

Organizational commitment is a subject that has been studied in the literature for many years. In this sense, the person's commitment to the organization of which he/she is a member is determined by other organizational, environmental and personal factors. Therefore, the concept of organizational commitment has been subjected to various classifications. When the definitions of organizational commitment are examined, it is seen that commitment is based on attitudinal and behavioral foundations. In other words, there are attitudinal and behavioral effects under the main reasons for the formation of loyalty of the members of the organization. The main reason why organizational commitment is classified in two different ways is that organizational behaviorists and social psychologists approach organizational commitment from different perspectives. Organizational behaviorists focus on attitudinal commitment while socio-psychologists focus on behavioral commitment (Sürücü & Maşlakçı, 2018).

One of the most cited studies in the field of classification of organizational commitment is Allen & Meyer (1993). Accordingly, commitment is a psychological condition that reflects the relationship between individuals and the organization. Therefore, organizational commitment points to a concrete network of relationships that can be observed directly, rather than an abstract situation (Allen & Meyer, 1993; Türköz et al., 2013). These researchers divide organizational commitment into three groups: "affective", "continuance", and "normative" commitment.

Affective commitment: It can be expressed as the intention to stay in the organization as a result of a kind of psychological contract between individuals and the organization. In other words, emotional commitment is the emotional integration of employees in organizations and their participation in organizational activities in line with the goals, plans and strategies determined by the organization and the main goals of the organization (Büyükyılmaz et al., 2018). In this sense, affective commitment is the willingness of the individual to stay in the organization at his/her own request. An individual feels emotionally natural towards the organization and is willing to continue to participate in the organization voluntarily.

Continuance commitment: It has two basic subjects consisting of continuance commitment, absence of business alternatives and negative side returns (Örücü & Kışlalıoğlu, 2014). In this sense, when we consider the expectations of individuals, continuous commitment is directly related to a number of achievements that organizations undertake to provide to individuals. The individual will continue his/her commitment to the organization until he/she achieves a more rational acquisition. In other words, it relates to the costs that people perceive to be faced as a result of their departure from the organization. Employees choose to stay in the organization when there are very high costs of ending membership in the organization. In the development of this commitment, people's perception that there are no other business alternatives, such as investments made within the organization (labor given for a long time, relationships owned, etc.), plays an important role (Çetin et al., 2011). Accordingly, continuance commitment refers to the conditions necessary for a person to remain in the organization.

Normative commitment: It emphasizes the tendency to be connected and loyal to institutions and organizations, as normative commitment provides socialization within a culture that encourages dedication and loyalty to the institution (Durna & Eren, 2011). Here, norms foster a sense of commitment to the organization and act as insurance against intention to leave. The level of normative commitment may vary according to the differences in the individual, family, social and cultural developments of the employees (Kurşunoglu & Tanrıoğlu, 2010).

It is possible to interpret more than one concept and phenomenon together in explaining the unknown aspects of organizations or the ongoing functioning. In this way, it is possible to discover related components and even establish causal relationships between them. In this sense, research on the metaphor of organizational DNA; determination of organization DNA profiles (Çetin, 2014), relationship between school DNA profiles and teachers' psychological capital (Bostancı et al., 2017), the impact of organizational DNA on management style (Kahraman, 2019), organizational DNA and organizational citizenship behavior of teachers (Bostancı & Tosun, 2019), organizational DNA and digital transformation (Nart, 2019) and the impact of organizational DNA on leadership style come to the fore. On the other hand, especially in organizational commitment studies where public employees and public managers are treated as subjects; toxic leadership and organizational commitment (Kahveci et al., 2019), the impact of positive management on commitment (Balay et al., 2017).

Organizational commitment and organizational DNA

Organizational DNA is an element that reveals the basic identity of the organization and determines the structure of the organization with its various components. From this point of view, the concept of organizational DNA has a decisive effect on the organizational commitment of employees, especially as a reflection of a significant part of intra-organizational factors.

One of the most important factors affecting an employee's organizational commitment is the management style of the organization. An organization's management style is one of the main elements that make up the organization's DNA, based on both external and internal factors, as well as the personal characteristics of managers. In organizations with a democratic management approach that adds the employee to management processes, the organizational commitment of the employees is high. Conversely, in organizations with a strict hierarchical management style, the organizational commitment of employees is low (Atik & Üstüner, 2014). It can be said that in organizations with an unhealthy organizational profile, management-oriented decision-making processes and situations where employees remain passive often occur. From this point of view, it can be stated that organizations with an unhealthy profile in terms of decision-making processes have a negative impact on the organizational commitment of their employees. If managers make careful decisions, it should be taken into account that employees' emotional commitment to the organization will increase. Managers should avoid adopting postponement, avoidance and panic decision-making styles when making decisions (Temur, 2012).

Organizational commitment is influenced by feedback mechanisms within the organization. This includes getting feedback on what the employee is doing, at what level and how efficiently. Information, one of the most important building blocks of organizational DNA, stands out here. Employees' knowledge of how their performance is measured, who makes organizational decisions, to whom they are responsible, and the details of job analysis increases their organizational commitment (Gülova & Demirsoy, 2012). From this perspective, organizational commitment begins with the employee's employment with a psychological contract and develops as the organization learns more about the organization's values, norms, and goals. In the case of the organizational DNA, managing the process of transferring information to an employee is an important variable in terms of emotional commitment. Employees with high emotional loyalty showed a better knowledge-sharing attitude towards each other and managers and were more successful. Individuals can share the information they have and the information they will receive from other employees in the organization if they are willing. It is accepted that employees will show a good attitude to sharing information if their emotional commitment is high (Taş, 2011).

The hierarchical structures of organizations and the concept of organizational commitment are closely related. The hierarchical structure of the organization is one of the main elements that determine its organizational DNA. In organizations with a strict hierarchy and vertical decision-making mechanisms, the organizational commitment of employees may be limited by the perspective of managers in the organization. But it seems that in organizations with a democratic structure, horizontal communication also experiences a high level, and in organizations that do not implement a strict hierarchy, the organizational commitment of those who work is higher. This is due to the fact that employees who can see that they will participate and contribute to the organizational structure at all levels find the managers of the organization more sincere (Erdem, 2007). Organizational DNA is directly influenced by the organizational structure, goals and goals of an organization. For this reason, the goals and objectives of each organization are not the same. In some organizations, strict hierarchical structure can sometimes be vital reasons. Organizational commitment is expected to be high, although with a strict hierarchical structure, in examples such as military institutions, space research institutions, and institutions providing production and logistics services for hazardous materials. But in sectors where social services such as hospitals, schools, hotels are more prominent, it seems that the organizational commitment of employees is higher in institutions with the resilient organizational DNA (Yalçın & İplik, 2005).

Motivators, one of the building blocks of organizational DNA, determine the compliance of employees with the goals of the organization, how much they associate their future with the organization and how satisfied they are with their career goals in the organization. From this point of view, the motive relationship is a mutual structure. The employee's commitment to the organization is directly related to the organization's strong desire to continue working for the employee. For this reason, ensuring the organizational commitment of employees depends on the degree to which the organization deals with individual problems. It is also about the degree to which employees view and adapt the activities of the organization in terms of their own goals. Organizational commitment occurs when the individual's attitudes and behaviors are compatible with the value system of the whole and other people in the organization (Albayrak, 2007). In addition, employees are more committed to their work, even though they are committed to their organizations. Because learning the job well and increasing the work experience will enable the employee to move organizations that offer better opportunities in the future.

Individuals believe that the effect of the work they do and what they learn from this job in their future career represents them more (Uygur, 2007).

A weak organizational commitment can be mentioned when the organization has little effect on the employee in terms of motivating factors. Studies examining the relationship between organizational commitment and stress suggest that employees with high organizational commitment are more affected by stress than other employees. Employees with high levels of commitment are also more sensitive to organizational issues, so they are more affected by organizational problems with the level of organizational danger and threat (Gülova & Demirsoy, 2012).

In the field, especially in public organizations, there was no study that linked the levels and perceptions of organizational commitment of public employees, who loaded almost the entire workload, with the DNA profiles of organizations. However, it can be stated that there may be a relationship between these two variables, and determining the boundaries of this relationship will contribute to the field.

The purpose of this study is to reveal the relationship between the employees' organizational DNA perceptions and the organizational commitment of the employees depending on the perceptions of the employees. For this purpose, the following hypotheses have been developed and tested:

H₁: Organizational DNA significantly affects organizational commitment.

H_{1a}: The just-in-time organization significantly influences the organizational commitment.

H_{1b}: The passive-aggressive organization significantly influences the organizational commitment.

H_{1c}: The fits-and-starts organization significantly influences the organizational commitment.

H_{1d}: The overmanaged organization significantly influences the organizational commitment.

Organizational DNA

Methodology

In this study, which was conducted to determine the effect of employees' organizational DNA perceptions on organizational commitment, firstly, information about the sample and scales was included, and then the analysis was made based on the model created in the light of the information obtained from the sample. In this context, a confirmatory factor analysis of each variable was first performed, and then a correlation between the variables was found. The findings were compared with the current field.

In this study, it was aimed to reveal the relationship between employees' organizational DNA perceptions and organizational commitment levels and to reveal the difference between employee demographic characteristics and organizational commitment levels. The correlational survey model was used in the research conducted within the framework of this purpose. The correlational survey model is intended to determine the presence, degree, of co-variation between multiple variables (Karasar, 2009).

Universe and sample of research

The universe of the research is composed of staff working in public institutions in Tarsus district of Mersin province. The sample selected from the universe was calculated by taking into account a 5% margin of error within 95% reliability limits. The sample of the study consists of 320 personnel selected from within the universe by the convenience sampling method. Of the respondents 51,8% (n=166) women; 10,9% (n=35) 25-34, %39,1 (n=125) 35-44, %39,1 (n=125) 45-54, 10,9% (n=35), 55 and over years old; %11,8 (n=38) associate degree, %76,4 (n=244) bachelor degree, %11,8 (n=38) MBA degree; %1,6 (n=5) 1-5 years, 8,5% (n=27) 6-10 years, 23,4% (n=75) 11-15 years, %15,9 (n=51) 6-20 years, %50,6 (n=162) 21 years and above work experience.

Data collection tools

Survey technique was used as a data collection tool in the research. The data were distributed through face-to-face interviews with respondents. The survey was conducted between 15/07/2020 and 05/09/2020. Of the 330 surveys distributed, 10 were removed because they were not suitable for analysis. Therefore, the analysis were conducted over 320 surveys. The questionnaire consisted of three sections and 46 questions. In the first part of the survey, there are seven questions about the demographic information of the respondents. In the second part of the survey, there is a scale of organizational commitment consisting of 18 questions. Finally, the last part of the survey involves organizational DNA scale.

The validity and reliability of the scales were tested before the analyses were performed. There are varieties of validity. Generally used validity types are (Kartal & Bardakçı, 2018): Appearance validity, scope validity, criteria validity and structure validity.

The most widely accepted measure of internal consistency is the Cronbach's alpha coefficient. Construct validity was not tested in the alternative scale, since the scale that provides the validity of the construct and taken as a criterion was not developed in determining the construct validity of the alternative scale. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) were performed to reveal the implicit structure of the scales. It is necessary to look at EFA before a confirmatory factor analysis is performed. Although these scales are accepted in the literature, basic component analyses should be performed before CFA to check whether the individuals who completed the survey perceive the survey dimensions correctly (Civelek, 2018).

EFA aims to determine how many sub-dimensions the items in a survey can be grouped under and what kind of relationship there is between them (Seçer, 2015). In the measurement tool with EFA, items are asked to be collected under certain sub-dimensions or factors. In EFA, it is expected that the load value of items contained in the scale will be at least 0,30, the item will be involved in each factor, and the difference will be at least 0,10 between the factors involved in the two factors.

Organizational DNA scale

The "Organizational DNA Scale" developed by Çetin & Döş (2014) was used to reveal employees' perceptions of the organizational DNA metaphor. The scale consists of a total of six dimensions and 28 items. Items on the scale are designed with a 5 Likert scale (1=Strongly disagree, 5=Strongly agree). Whether the data collected from the study group are suitable for factor analysis was examined with the help of the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) coefficient and the Barlett's test. As a result of the first analysis, a five-factor structure explaining 58.318% of the total variance was obtained, 17th question was not covered by any factors, questions 3rd, 25th and 28th were removed and the analysis was repeated because it did not provide the requirement for a difference of at least 0,10 between the factors involved in the two factors. As a result of the 2nd analysis, a five-factor structure was obtained that explained 59.456% of the total variance, but since the 22nd and 26th questions again did not provide the requirement for a difference of at least 0.10 between the factors involved in the two factors, these questions were also removed from the scale and the analysis was repeated. As a result of the analysis of the article, the 5th, 7th, 8th and 21st questions with values below 0.30 were also excluded from the scale. KMO coefficient as a result of the analysis after these questions were removed. It has been calculated as 0,886. According to the results of the Barlett's test, there were high correlation relationships between items ($\chi^2=2297,065$; $p<0.001$). According to these findings, it was concluded that the dataset was suitable for factor analysis. However, in the analysis of the item, this item was also removed from the scale due to the negative value of the 6th item. Each variance value for the factor structure of the scale was found to be more than 0.10, resulting in a four-factor structure explaining 62.928% of the total variance.

The load value of the items in the first factor varies between .589 and .824. This factor, which accounts for 36.836% of the total variance, is the "just-in-time organization" sub-dimension. The charge value of the items in the second factor varies between .600 and .804. This factor, which accounts for 11.354% of the total variance, is the sub-dimension of the "passive-aggressive organization". The value of the items in the third factor varies between .565 and .805. This factor, which accounts for 8.732% of the total variance, is the sub-dimension of the "fits-and-starts organization" as inspirations-beginnings. The value of the items in the fourth factor varies between .584 and .785. This factor, which accounts for 6.006% of the total variance, is the sub-dimension of the "overmanaged organization".

Item analysis was performed to determine the separative strength of the organizational commitment scale. As a result of the analysis, the adjusted item-total correlations of the organizational DNA scale were ranked between .453 and .665. Results are given in Table 1. Data on correlation values between subdimensions of the organizational DNA scale are given in Table 2.

Table1.Factor loads of items of the organizational DNA scale, variances explained by subdimensions and matter analysis

Item	Just-in-Time	Passive-Aggressive	The Fits-and-Starts	Overmanaged	Item-Total Correlation
DNA9	.824				.485
DNA12	.808				.665
DNA11	.749				.472
DNA10	.672				.636
DNA2	.643				.538
DNA1	.589				.584
DNA24		.804			.536
DNA23		.760			.497
DNA27		.685			.453
DNA4		.600			.455
DNA15			.805		.627
DNA14			.803		.479
DNA16			.683		.647
DNA13			.565		.544
DNA18				.785	.396
DNA19				.729	.451
DNA20				.584	.618
Eigenvalues	6.262	1.930	1.484	1.021	
Variance Explained	36.836	11.354	8.732	6.006	
Total Variance Explained %			62.928		

Table2. Correlation between lower dimensions of the organizational DNA scale

	Just-in-time	Passive-Aggressive	The Fits-and-Starts	Overmanaged
Just-in-Time	1			
Passive-Aggressive	.422**	1		
The Fits-and-Starts	.476**	.481**	1	
Overmanaged	.415**	.404**	.552**	1

**p<0.01

The data in Table 2 show that there is a moderately significant and positive relationship between all four subdimensions. Whether the organizational DNA scale is supported by the collected data was tested with alternative models and it was seen that the 2nd level multi-factor model was the best fit. (CMIN/df=2.502; GFI=.900; CFI=.916; RMSEA=.072). Confirmatory factor analysis results are shown in Table 3. As a result of the reliability analysis, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient of the scale was calculated as 0.888, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient of the full-time organization from the lower dimensions of the scale was 0.846, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient of the passive-aggressive organization was 0.768, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient of the inspirations-beginnings organization was 0.805, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient of the overmanaged organization was 0.691.

Table3. The results of CFA

Item	Variable	Standardized Factor Load	Unstandardized Factor Load	Standard Error	Critic Ratio
DNA9		.692	1		
DNA12		.853	.906	.069	13.133
DNA11	Just-in-Time	.627	.800	.068	11.792
DNA10		.733	.684	.059	11.662
DNA2		.640	.675	.065	10.326
DNA1		.633	.755	.074	10.216
DNA4		.526	1		
DNA27	Passive-Aggressive	.607	1.118	.144	7.739
DNA23		.750	1.404	.162	8.659
DNA24		.842	1.571	.175	8.969
DNA13	The Fits-and-	.652	1		

DNA16	Starts	.878	1.224	.121	10.151
DNA15		.771	1.141	.119	9.580
DNA14		.562	.832	.106	7.866
DNA19		.521	1		
DNA18	Overmanaged	.458	.688	.088	7.832
DNA20		.776	.601	.086	6.967

Organizational Commitment Scale

The Organizational Commitment Questionnaire (OCQ) with 18 items and 3 sub-dimensions, developed by Meyer, Allen & Smith (1993) and adapted into Turkish language by Dağlı, Elçiçek & Han (2018), was used to determine the organizational commitment levels of the employees.

Whether the data collected from the study group are suitable for factor analysis was examined with the help of the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) coefficient and the Barlett's test. As a result of the initial analysis, it was determined that the data was suitable for factor analysis and a 4-factor structure was revealed, which explains 57.887% of the total variance. But 16th question was not covered by any factors. In determining the items to be included in the CFA, there must be a difference of at least .10 between the factors involved in the two factors (Seçer, 2017). In this context, questions 7, 11 and 13 were removed from the scale and the analysis was repeated because they did not meet this requirement. As a result of the analysis, the KMO coefficient was calculated as .872. This value is quite acceptable and means that the sample size is sufficient for factor analysis. According to the results of the Barlett's test, there are high correlation relationships between items, so it can be said that the data came from multiple normal distributions ($\chi^2=1744.176$; $p<0.001$). According to these findings, it was concluded that the dataset was suitable for factor analysis.

For the factor structure of the scale, the common variance value explained by each item must be at least .10 (Seçer, 2017). For this purpose, a table of "Communalities" was examined, in which each item has a rate of explaining the variance in a common factor together, and it was seen that this condition was met, a 3-factor structure was obtained that explains 60.124% of the total variance. The charge value of the items in the first factor varies between .546 and .775. This factor, which accounts for 37.772% of the total variance, is the sub-dimension of "normative commitment". The charge value of the items in the second factor varies between .550 and .775. This factor, which accounts for 13.110% of the total variance on the scale, is the sub-dimension of "affective commitment". The value of the items in the third factor varies between .769 and .852. This factor, which accounts for 9.292% of the total variance, is the sub-dimension of "continuance commitment".

Item analysis was performed to determine the separative strength of the organizational commitment scale. As a result of the analysis, the adjusted item-total correlations of the organizational commitment scale were ranked between .371 and .704. Considering that items with a value of .30 and above are considered sufficient in terms of distinguishing the property to be measured in the interpretation of the item-total correlation, it can be said that the item-total correlation is sufficient. The findings are shown in Table 4. Data on correlation values between subdimensions of the organizational commitment scale are given in Table 5.

The data in Table 5 show a moderately significant and positive relationship between all three sub-dimensions. Whether the organizational commitment scale was supported by collected data was tested with alternative models and the 2nd order multifactor model was the best fit model (CMIN/df=2.521; GFI=.925; CFI=.933; RMSEA=.069). The results of confirmatory factor analysis are shown in Table 6.

As a result of the reliability analysis, Cronbach's alpha coefficient of the scale was found .862, the sub-dimensions of the scale Cronbach's alpha coefficient were lower size .837 normative commitment, affective commitment .817 lower size of the Cronbach's alpha coefficient, Cronbach's alpha coefficient was calculated as .744 continuance commitment to the lower size.

Table 4. Factor loadings of items of the organizational commitment scale, variances explained by subdimensions and item analysis

Item	Normative Commitment	Affective Commitment	Continuance Commitment	Item Total Correlation
OB17	.821			.587
OB15	.794			.401
OB18	.707			.371
OB4	.685			.415
OB14	.655			.381
OB5	.546			.617
OB1		.775		.704
OB6		.757		.666
OB2		.755		.524

	OB3		.632		.438
	OB10		.550		.617
	OB9			.852	.583
	OB12			.778	.511
	OB8			.769	.550
	Eigenvalues	5.281	1.835	1.301	
	Variance Explained	37.722	13.110	9.292	
	Total Variance Explained %		60.124		

Table5. Correlation between lower dimensions of the organizational commitment scale

	Normative Commitment	Affective Commitment	Continuance Commitment
Normative Commitment	1		
Affective Commitment	.595**	1	
Continuance Commitment	.217**	.328**	1

**p<0.01

Table6. Confirmatory factor analysis results

Item	Var.	Standardized Factor Load	Unstandardized Factor Load	Standart Error	Critic Ratio
OB12		.527	1		
OB14		.720	1.399	.161	8.706
OB4	Normative	.751	1.497	.168	8.890
OB18	Commitment	.647	1.187	.145	8.210
OB15		.737	1.505	.171	8.811
OB17		.694	1.357	.159	8.540
OB10		.603	1		
OB3	Affective	.827	1.448	.134	10.844
OB2	Commitment	.510	.718	.093	7.691
OB6		.796	1.241	.117	10.623
OB1		.686	1.245	.129	9.644
OB5	Continuance	.700	1		
OB4	Commitment	.853	1.138	.116	9.793
OB8		.589	.929	.103	8.998

Findings and Discussion

Descriptive Information Between Variables

Descriptive information about the dependent and independent variable is given in Table 7.

Table7. Descriptive information

Variables	Total	Min.	Max.	$\bar{x}$	Sd.
Organizational DNA	320	1	5	3.781	.555
Organizational Commitment	320	1	5	3.524	.662

Relationships Between Variables

In order to determine the relationships between variables, the Pearson Correlation coefficient was calculated and given in Table 8. As a result of the analysis, it was determined that there is a significant relationship between organizational DNA and its sub-dimensions and organizational commitment and sub-dimensions.

Table 8. Correlation values

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Normative Commitment	1						
Affective Commitment	.595**	1					
Continuance Commitment	.217**	.328**	1				
Just-in-time	.508**	.565**	.257**	1			
Passive-Aggressive	.222**	.384**	.302**	.422**	1		
The fits-and-starts	.251**	.374**	.343**	.476**	.481**	1	
Overmanaged	.156**	.368**	.299**	.415**	.404**	.552**	1

**p<0.001

Hypothesis Tests

In order to determine the linear relations between variables, the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable with another expression, regression analysis was performed. Regression model coefficients are shown in Table 9.

Table 9. Regression Model Coefficients

Model		Coefficients				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	β		
1	Constant	.909	.209		4.358	.000
	Organizational DNA	.692	.055	.579	12.672	.000
1	Constant	1.404	.164		8.553	.000
	The just-in-Time	.553	.042	.593	13.142	.000
1	Constant	2.107	.245		8.583	.000
	The passive-aggressive	.448	.060	.384	7.409	.000
1	Constant	2.348	.156		15.101	.000
	The fits-and-starts	.336	.043	.399	7.749	.000
1	Constant	2.376	.187		12.674	.000
	The overmanaged	.306	.049	.330	6.236	.000

As a result of the regression analysis, H_1 , H_{1a} , H_{1b} , H_{1c} and H_{1d} hypotheses were accepted.

Conclusion and Implications

This research, which aims to examine the organizational DNA perceptions and organizational commitment levels of public employees, was completed in 2020 as a result of the analysis of the data obtained from a total of 320 participants. According to the results of the analysis, it was understood that the data on both the organizational DNA perception and organizational commitment level of public employees showed a normal distribution and it was decided to continue the analysis with parametric methods.

The overall aim of this study was to reveal the relationship between the perceptions of public employees' organizational DNA and their organizational commitment according to the perceptions of employees. In this way, it is aimed to examine the concept of organizational DNA, which is a widely studied area in the literature, and to determine whether there is a relationship between organizational DNA and organizational commitment. In this section, the results attained from the findings obtained within the scope of the research and the discussions associated with the field are given.

As part of the research, it is aimed to reveal the profile of the organization's DNA in the organizations in which they work according to the perceptions of public employees. Accordingly, the "organizational DNA" scale was applied to the participants and the data were subjected to statistical analysis. According to the data obtained, public employees' perceptions of organizational DNA are "The just-in-time organization, the passive-aggressive organization, the fits-and-starts organization and the overmanaged organization".

One of the hypotheses tested within the scope of the research was constructed and tested as "Organizational DNA significantly affects organizational commitment". Based on the results of the analysis, it was found that there is a significant relationship between organizational DNA and its sub-dimensions, as well as organizational commitment. A similar study found that its employees generally tend to show strong organizational commitment to the institution in which they work (Battal, 2020). Meydan, Basım & Çetin (2011) emphasizes that, in accordance with the expectations expressed in the field, perception of justice can have a positive impact on organizational commitment, and these two variables together can have a negative impact on individuals' burnout level. Therefore, it can be stated that a high level of organizational commitment will make significant contributions to the organization and individuals.

As part of organizational commitment, it was found that there was a significant difference between employees aged 55 and over and people in the age group of 25-34 and 35-44; between associate graduates and bachelor degree; between people with 20 years of experience and over and those with 6-15 years of experience; there was no difference between groups within the scope of organizational DNA. A study conducted by Ovalı, Demir, & Baştürk (2020) showed that participants' perceptions of organizational commitment according to the gender variable differed in their perceptions of affective commitment and their perceptions of normative and continuance commitment were similar. On the other hand, it has been concluded that seniority year and age variables have an effect on organizational commitment. Accordingly, as the year of seniority and age progressed, it took its place among the findings that there was an increase in all three types of commitment. Similarly Eyiöl (2020) found that the level of affective commitment of employees differs significantly from the year of work in the institution, and the level of affective commitment increases as the year of work in the institution increases. A high level of loyalty is desirable in the field, because an employee with a high level of loyalty is identified with his organization and enjoys being a member of the organization (Allen & Meyer, 1990; Balçık, 2018).

Based on the results of regression analysis, organizational DNA explains 34% of organizational commitment. By examining the standardized β and t value, it can be said that organizational DNA is a meaningful predictor of organizational commitment. Looking at the relevant field, it was found that the DNA of the organization is associated with variables such as psychological capital (Bostancı et al., 2017), management style (Kahraman, 2019) and organizational citizenship behavior (Bostancı & Tosun, 2019). Accordingly, it can be argued that there is a relationship between organizational commitment and perception of the organizational DNA, which is considered to have a direct and indirect relationship with the aforementioned variables.

On the other hand, organizational DNA, along with all its sub-dimensions, is a meaningful predictor of organizational commitment and all its sub-dimensions. Based on the findings and results of this research, the following recommendations were made; (1) In-depth interviews and longitudinal studies can be conducted that will reveal the impact of gender roles at the level of organizational DNA and organizational commitment. (2) Given that employees have different perceptions according to the age and seniority variable, the dynamism of young employees and the experience of older employees should be blended, thus saving corporate organizations from being only old age and experienced or only young and inexperienced organizations. (3) Activities can be organized within the scope of professional development activities for employees and managers in order to ensure organizational harmony of employees and to provide more positive perceptions. (4) By taking into account the positive correlation between organizational DNA perception and organizational commitment levels, structural reforms can be implemented that will positively affect employees' attitudes towards the organization. (5) This research was carried out using quantitative research method and similar research can be conducted using different dependent and independent variables. (6) Qualitative research can be conducted to confirm the results obtained in this research and to obtain more in-depth information.

There are also some limitations of this research. The most important limitation of the research is that the research is not longitudinal and only conducted in the public sector. Different results can be obtained if the research is conducted in other sectors. In subsequent studies, it may be suggested to examine the DNA of the organization in different sectors and together with other variables evaluated within the scope of organizational behavior.

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